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Effects of Code Switching Among College Instructors and Students in a Philippine Classroom Setting

Louie B. Villanueva^{1*}, Bert A. Gamiao²

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ABSTRACT

Code-switching exists in many countries particularly in multilingual communities such as the City of Laoag in Ilocos Norte, Philippines. The researchers ventured into the occurrence of code-switching at Mariano Marcos State University specifically the College of Teacher Education and College of Industrial Technology, looked into its effects and made some implications. Thus, after securing permission to conduct the research in the respondents' respective institutions, the researchers recorded, transcribed and analyzed the classroom discourses to bring about the effects of code switching committed by both the instructors and the students. Using descriptive-qualitative analysis and in-depth interview (IDI), the researchers examined the effects of code-switching among Filipino college instructors and students. They also identified some implications of the effects of code-switching in Philippine college classrooms. This approach seeks to describe, decode, translate, and otherwise come to terms with the meaning of certain more or less naturally occurring phenomena in the social world. The following effects to teaching and learning were inferred: *code switching helps students to better understand directions, eradicates language barrier for a clearer instruction, promotes better understanding by students, helps them in generating a better choice, ensures semantic understanding among students, and aids the students to investigate further, to clarify, to verify, or to confirm an earlier knowledge.* All of these are directed towards achieving a better performance of the teachers and students. Based on the findings, it is concluded that code switching is a big help to facilitate better teaching and learning in Philippine college classrooms.

INTRODUCTION

Learning a second language takes time and involves a number of factors and miscommunication could be one. Miscommunication is defined by Hamzah and Fei (2020) and Edwards, Bybee, Frost, Harvey, & Navarro (2017) as an insufficient understanding and misinterpretation of information of decoded information in a communication. And during the learning process, the learner tends to stick to the rules of the L1 and may have difficulty in applying the rules of L2. Hence, there is a tendency of mixing languages in an utterance thereby committing switching of codes. The term code refers to speech varieties or dialects in a language or even languages. This is widely used in the field of linguistics, and it is studied always in a social context. Further, it is a signal used by the speaker to convey some message. The term code switching means shifting from one language variety to another when the situation demands (Richards, et al, 1985).

Similarly, Skiba (1997), Lin (2013) stated that code-switching as the alternation between two codes (languages and/or dialects), between people who share those particular codes and Nordquist (2020) stated that it occurs far more in conversation than in writing. Choices about how code-switching manifests itself are determined by a number of social and linguistic factors. It is quite typical in multicultural and immigrant populations. Code switching can take on several forms including alteration of sentences, phrases from both languages, and switching in a long narrative. In normal conversations between two bilinguals, code-switching consists of eighty-four percent

single word switches, ten percent phrase switches, and six percent clause switching.

According to Gumperz (1982), code switching is the juxtaposition within the same speech exchange of passages of speech belonging to two different grammatical systems or subsystems. Simply put, code-switching can be defined as the alternation of languages be it in a face-to-face setting or online modality such as in Facebook ads as studied by Kuo, Hou, and Hsieh (2021).

However, not all cases of alternation of languages are cases of code switching. Several sociolinguists distinguish between code switching and code mixing. For example, in several studies, code switching and code mixing refer to intersentential and intrasentential language alternation, respectively. In other words, code mixing can be understood as the switching of languages that occurs within sentences, usually at the level of words or idiomatic expressions. However, code mixing must also be distinguished from borrowing in that borrowings are used to fill lexical gaps by monolinguals, while code mixing is employed at every level of lexical and syntactic structure by bilinguals. Moreover, borrowings are completely assimilated to the borrowing language, whereas mixed elements often retain features of the donor language (Gibbons, 1987).

LITERATURE REVIEW

A lot of authors around the globe have dealt with the processes of code switching, code mixing and borrowing, not all of them have provided clear-cut distinctions for

¹ Assistant Professor and Teaching Internship Coordinator of Secondary Education Department, MMSU Philippines.

² Associate Professor Bert A. Gamiao is the Chief of the Center for Teaching Excellence (CTEX), MMSU, Philippines.

* Corresponding author's e-mail: lbvillanueva@mmsu.edu.ph

such phenomena. Code switching and borrowing are explained as a continuum in progression in which code switching precedes borrowing in time and is more restricted in its use (individual vs. societal). In Pahta's (2004) words:

"The distinction between the two may seem straightforward in theory: switching involves the use of two languages in one utterance, whereas the term 'borrowing' is used of embedded elements that have been integrated into the host language."

Moreover, as stated by Pahta (2004), code switching can be both situational and metaphorical. Situational code switching occurs when the codes are used depending upon the situations. Situational code switching does not involve any topic change. When a situation of speaker changes, the codes used also change. Here, a change of topic requires a change of language. The process of changing the codes has connections with the social value and status of speakers. Since, they are deciding the codes to be selected.

On the other hand, code mixing occurs when the speakers use two or more languages together and mix them in a single utterance or in their communicative act. For example, a person speaking to an educated person or to an honored person in the society, he uses a standard variety. At the same time, when he speaks to the person who is socially lower in status' he uses a low variety. But, when he speaks with his family friends or other related persons, he mixes both the high and low varieties of the languages. In a casual conversational situation, there will be a mixture of both the codes.

Sometimes, a person who knows more than one dialect uses different codes. A person who belongs to one particular dialect may use a standard code in formal situation or with his friends. At the same time, he may change from one code to another assuming that the hearer also knows the change in the code. In a bilingual situation also code switching occurs. A person who knows two languages may know the cultural background of both the languages, and sometimes becomes proficient in both the languages and thereby he adopts code switching during language use.

Additionally, code switching exists in a bilingual community and speakers often switch between languages in conversation without any advance notice (Yacovone, Moya and Snedeker, 2021). This is also possible in a multilingual situation; when a speaker uses more than two languages, he often switches over from one to another and ends up mixing all the codes. This is common in multilingual communities and classes like Ilokano classrooms in Laoag City, Ilocos Norte, the Philippines. There are various perspectives on code switching. The practice of code switching itself does not indicate a deficiency of language knowledge; rather, it seems to serve a communicative function in conversation. Code switching as a conversational resource has been studied by several sociolinguists. Blom and Gumperz (1972) distinguished two types of code switching, situational code switching and metaphorical code switching.

Situational code switching is related to a change in situation, for instance, when a new participant joins the activity, or a change in the conversation topic or setting. On the other hand, metaphorical code-switching is often used as a conversational strategy to enhance or mitigate conversational acts such as requests, denials, topic shifts, elaborations or clarifications. Gumperz (1982) later re-labeled metaphorical code switching as conversational code switching.

Code switching can be used by teachers by integrating it into the activities used to teach a second language. By having students get in pairs and switch languages at pre-determined points in conversation, it helps them to learn each other's language. Teachers can also begin a lesson in one language, then switch to another language, forcing the children to listen carefully and comprehend both languages (Skiba, 1997).

Some effects of code switching are also worth noting in this section. The possible effect(s) the switching can have on the acquisition of the English language can be summarized thus, a) the switching enables students to discuss freely with their friends, teachers and parents at home and other settings; b) it helps them to understand new concepts better if explained in L1 which means that there are some subjects more effectively explained when switching languages; c) it is because they do not know the word for it in the other language and that the word is readily recalled in the switched language; and d) it serves as a status symbol. Switching here serves as a directive function wherein it involves the hearer directly.

The interest in studying code switching functions is not new as it goes back to as far as 1975 as Lance investigated whether code switching had any syntactic restrictions, but he concluded that there were none. Ibrahim et al. (2013) stated in their findings that teachers positively perceive code-switching in the classroom. The same result was found out by Rivera and Mazak (2017) wherein students in their study had neutral to positive perceptions of code-switching. Thus, they normally code-switched in the classroom just like any other L2 learners.

An important work on code mixing is Gibbons' (1979) study on U-Gay-Wa. In his work, Gibbons examined the nature of the language mixture of the students at the University of Hong Kong. U-Gay-Wa was predominantly Cantonese with a less significant English element and some interesting autonomous elements. He found some of the code-mixed sentences difficult to analyze because the structure of the mixture agreed with neither language system. He proposed that in syntax, there was a small autonomous U-Gay-Wa element. He concluded that the students had complete competence in neither Cantonese nor English. They developed an independent system – a fused competence – to cope with every facet of their daily life, this competence of necessity involving the mixing of elements from the sources of Cantonese and English.

The most comprehensive work on syntactic constraints on code switching comes from Poplack (1980), and Poplack and Sankoff (1988). They suggested two major

constraints in code-switching, namely: the Equivalence Constraint and the Free Morpheme Constraint. After surveying the structural integrity of the component languages in code-switching, they argued for a separate grammar of code switching in addition to the two monolingual grammars. Ten major switch types were found in their studies.

Another vital contribution to the existing literature in the field of code switching is by the anthropological linguist Ana Celia Zentella who studied Puerto Rican children residing in New York (1997). This research was conducted through an observation as well as audio and video recording over a span of 14 years. Zentella followed the lives of five Puerto Rican girls from childhood to adulthood to determine the reasons for the use of multiple language varieties found in their complex speech community. The code-switching styles of the five subjects were described along with the factors that trigger them. In addition to performing cultural work, Zentella discovered that code switching performs important conversational work as evidenced by her discovery of the use of code switching to accomplish 22 conversational strategies which she classified under three major categories.

Despite the significant findings of the foregoing studies abroad, a more specific review is imperative to contextualize this present study; thus, this section presents some studies on code switching done in the Philippines.

In 1978, Pascasio studied the functions of code switching in business domains among Filipino bilinguals. She identified six sociocultural functions which cause code switches: the role relationship of the interlocutor (status, position), age, sex, topics, speech functions and domains. Apart from factors that affect the code switches, she also identified the function it plays. These code switches were found to be used for quotation, interjection, repetition, message qualification, addressee specification, inquiring and giving information, personalization versus objectification, and to express politeness.

Corollary to this, Bautista (2004) claimed the alternation of Tagalog and English in informal discourse is a feature of the linguistic repertoire of educated, middle and upper-class Filipinos. Her paper described the linguistic structure and sociolinguistic functions of Tagalog-English code switching (Taglish) as provided by various researchers through the years. The analysis of Taglish began with a linguistic focus, segmenting individual utterances into sentences and studying the switch points within the sentence. It was found out that Taglish has been viewed as a mode of discourse and a linguistic resource in the bilingual's repertoire. New theoreticians working within a Critical Discourse Analysis framework are seeing Taglish as a reaction to the hegemonizing tendencies of Philippine society and modern life.

Theoretical background

This research is anchored on Social Interactionist Theory by Vygotsky (1934). This stresses the significance of the environment and the context in which the language is being learned. It focuses on the pragmatics of language

rather than grammar, which should come later. In this theory, the beginning speaker and the experienced speaker – be they child and adult or second-language learner and fluent speaker – exist in a negotiated arrangement where feedback is always possible.

The basic appeal of this theory is the importance it places on the home and the cultural environment in early-childhood language acquisition. Language on this perspective is not an innate ability. Rather, it develops in negotiating the environment. Hence, vocabulary is bound by context or, alternatively, by the culture within which speech is necessary and understandable.

This approach to language acquisition is based on culture and environment. Thus, it is not universal in scope. In fact, the theory holds that language is never universal, but always context- and time-bound. On one hand, this means that language seems to be provincial, but also utilitarian, because it develops in the environment where it is most needed and most likely to be understood. On the other hand, it keeps the level of basic comprehension solely on the level of the initial environment (http://www.ehow.com/about_5465173).

According to Vygotsky, social interaction plays an important role in the learning process. He proposed the zone of proximal development (ZPD), where learners construct the new language through socially mediated interaction (Brown, 2000). Vygotsky places more emphasis on society, the social context of learning. ZPD refers to the layer of skill or knowledge which is just beyond that with which the learner is currently capable of coping. There are two levels of development in ZPD: the actual development level and the potential development level. The actual development level refers to the individual's ability to perform certain activities independently of another individual. In the potential level, the individual can perform the activities when help or support is given. The difference between the two levels is the distance between the actual developmental level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem solving under adult guidance in collaboration with more capable peers.

Ellis (1994) supported Vygotsky's view and said that learners are socially interactive. They are not to be considered as an associative network, a mechanistic processor of information, relatively unembodied, unconscious, monologic, unsituated, asocial, uncultured, and untutored.

This theory provides valuable insights into how learners acquire and use language as they interact with their peers and teachers whose English is their second language. Further, it suggests that instruction must be designed in ways that will suit the nature of ESL in the Philippines, the learners, and the society.

Hence, this study explored the effects of code-switching among Filipino college instructors and students and identified some implications of the effects of code-switching in Philippine college classrooms.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive-qualitative approach using classroom recordings from the online classes of three English, three Science and three Mathematics instructors and their students at Mariano Marcos State University-College of Teacher Education and College of Industrial Technology as well as an in-depth interview (IDI) to further gather pertinent data and support for this endeavor. Researcharticles.com (2020) and Kumar (2011) stated that descriptive-qualitative research design answers 4WH questions such as what, who, where, and when. Answers to these questions do not necessarily provide first hand experiments, or observations, hence, the researchers ask these questions from people who know about the phenomenon and gathers information from secondary sources like books and periodicals and among others which may supplement the study. Further, this approach seeks to describe, decode, translate, and otherwise come to terms with the meaning of certain more or less naturally occurring phenomena in the social world. Having secured permission to conduct the research in the respondents' respective institutions, the researchers recorded, transcribed and analyzed the classroom discourses to bring about the effects of code switching committed by both the teachers and the students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of Code Switching among College Instructors and Students

This section presents the effects or results of code switching in college classes among teachers and students. The researchers were guided by Muysken's (2000) effects of code switching to identify the effects or consequences. Extracts from the discourses of college instructors and students were used to better illustrate the main points for each effect. Specifically, effects on the use of code switching in classes where English is the medium of instruction, are discussed in the succeeding paragraphs.

Effects of Teachers' Code Switching

Code switching helps students to better understand directions. Giving of instructions to students is very vital in teaching. Hence, to ensure students' comprehension of directions, teachers resort to code switching. Doing so will enable students to carry out the expected output because they have fully understood the directions.

The giving of clear directions using Filipino and Ilocano is manifested in the following extracts:

Example 1.

Ilagay natin dito sa (Let's put in) another place, *ilagay sa* (put in the) test tube, *ihalo sa* (mix with the) plant weeds doon sa (therein the) extract *at doon sa ginawa inilagay natin, padadamihin natin yan aasim di yan at magiging* (and with what we did, we will regenerate that until it becomes sour and it becomes an) alcohol.- HEI4S

Example 2.

Step 1 *kuma, agdetermine kayo ti* (you will determine the) topic right, but to make it easier, *inted ko ti topic un*, so *awan problema kadetan*. (I already gave your topic so there is no

problem anymore). - HEI3E

Example 3.

Q-2 is equal to square root of X. *Yan ang ilagay niyo*. (You put that). - HEI2M

It can be inferred from these examples that the teacher switches to Filipino and Ilocano in giving instructions. Hence, majority of the switching denotes an action (*ilagay, ihalo, padamihin, agdtermine, inted and ilagay*).

Moreover, these instructions which are embodied in action words are switched to Filipino. Although Filipino is also the second language of Filipino students aside from English, the degree of comprehension is higher than in English.

Code switching eradicates language barrier for a clearer instruction. The use of English alone in the discussion may result to poor comprehension among the students. This can be attributed to the practice of speaking their vernacular at home.

In example 2, most of the switches of the teacher were done in Ilocano. This is to make sure that there is no language barrier since Ilocano is their vernacular. Hence, the switching ensures for a clearer comprehension and also a higher degree of emphasis. These all lead to a better and clearer picture of the instructions so students will not be lost in carrying out what is expected of them. As a result, they will be able to apply correct instructions during examinations, activities, and even in the preparation of their projects, all for the upliftment of their class standing. This is strengthened by the claim of one teacher as he explicitly stated:

"One of the weaknesses of students especially Maritime and Criminology is comprehension. They pretend that they understand during the giving of instructions but eventually, they would present a bad project or would carry out wrong moves during an activity. Using Ilocano or Filipino therefore, is of big help."

- HEI3ETR1

Code switching promotes better understanding by students. The practice of asking questions has a big spot in teaching. Questions translate the lesson into more concrete and attainable activities. Yet, in their process of asking questions, teachers intentionally switch to a more familiar language to effect better understanding among students. This is illustrated in the next examples:

Example 4.

Any questions on the boys at the back. *Okay lang kayo?* (Are you okay?)- HEI3S

Example 5.

No, c'mon you tell, *ana?* (what is it?) - HEI2E

In example 4, the teacher clarifies if the students can follow the discussion by asking them first in an English sentence followed by Filipino (*Okay lang kayo?*). In example 5, the teacher asks a student but the latter is seemingly reluctant to share what she knows. The use of the Ilocano tag (*ana*) adds to the authority of the teacher. On the other hand, the use of the familiar Ilocano term can also convince the student to speak. These switches are done in Filipino and Ilocano but this time in a form of a question.

By using code switching in asking questions, students will have a clearer grasp of the meaning of the question thus, they are motivated to answer and are able to generate more ideas. This contributes eventually to the development of a better comprehension strategy of students. If this becomes a practice, better results will be yielded. This claim finds support to this statement of a teacher respondent:

“No matter how beautifully crafted the questions are if the students do not understand them, the objective of asking still cannot be attained. Instead, asking it directly in the language they are comfortable with, as long as there is communication, could be a better strategy.”

- HEI3TR2

Code switching helps students in generating a better choice. Decision making or choosing which one is better is very challenging in teaching and learning. This is well executed by the teacher in the following example, that is, giving options for the students to do:

Example 6.

Alright, next, palm held vertically, what do you mean by say vertically? *Pwedeng “hi”, pwede namang “hi” pwede namang ganyan* (It could be Hi, it could also be Hi, that can be one) so it’s up to you. - HEI4E

The teacher in example 6 offers an alternative as an explanation to the topic. The giving of possible things to do is expressed in Filipino (*Pwedeng “hi”, pwede namang “hi” pwede namang ganyan*). The students can choose better because it is demonstrated well and the tone is more conversational.

However, in doing so, she switches to Filipino which is a language they are more comfortable with. This code-switching aids in understanding the situation hence, influences the decision making of the students. Apparently, code switching helps the students choose which one is the best. This holds true as one teacher respondent admitted, thus:

“I use Filipino and even Ilocano in teaching for the students to be guided especially when they are asked to choose. Their choice predicts possible outcome, so right from there, they have to choose which likely is the best.” - HEI3TR3

Effects of Students’ Code Switching

Code switching ensures semantic understanding among students. Learning a concept or following a task no matter how simple it is entails full understanding of the language used. To justify an answer is a daunting task for students. They are not only evaluated by rightness or wrongness of the answer but also the way they explain the process of arriving at the answer. This is where the employment of an effective and more familiar language comes in. This is evident in the succeeding examples where the switching is done in Ilocano:

Example 1.

And the addition property as the inverse, *inverse inkwa tay manen, inaply tayo so, alaen yo detoy, detoy neb, detoy.* (we applied inverse so we get this.) - HEI4M

Example 2.

Kinompute tayo detoy (We computed for this) sir, positive

ken(and) negative so cancel. - HEI4M

In examples 1 and 2, the students are explaining how they arrived at an answer. In doing so, they inserted non-English terms to their utterances. Evidently, switching between English and Ilocano can be seen in the use of the expressions *inkwa tay manen, in apply tayo so, alaen yo detoy, detoy neb, detoy* and *kinompute tayo detoy*.

This ensures semantic understanding among students and gives them comfort in processing the information. Full grasp of the contents of the utterance is attained plus the chance to inquire, clarify or add or even assess in the justification of the answer. This can be justified in most of the responses of the students, one of them stated the following:

“I cannot explain in straight English because I may run out of words. I’m afraid also that my grammar is not correct. My classmates might laugh at me, so ag Ilocano ak latta nukwan nu awan malagip ko Englishben.” - HEI3SR1

Code switching aids the students to investigate further, to clarify, to verify, or to confirm an earlier knowledge. In a usual classroom setting, there are only a few who would participate in the discussion. But considering an interactive topic in Math, Science and English classes, students’ participation is expected. These are manifested in the following examples:

Example 3.

Mabalin kami *nukwa aginternet*, Sir? (Can we use the internet, Sir?) - HEI3E

Example 4.

I think, potassium nitrate *.Usto Ma’am?* (Is this true Ma’am?) - HEI5S

Example 5.

Only in the Philippines. *Usto met neb.* (It’s right.) - HEI4S

Example 6.

What can you say? O bakit walang palakpak? Why there was no applause?) - HEI2E

In these examples, switching is exhibited by the use of the Ilocano prefix and words such as *ag (aginternet)* in example 3, *usto* in example 4, and *ustu met neb* in example 5. In example 6, the use of the Filipino sentence is evident after an English sentence.

It can be inferred that these lines are uttered in Filipino and Ilocano in search for answers of their questions. They can be categorically described as information-seeking questions, clarification-seeking questions and questions for agreement or disagreement. Simply put, the information they had is coupled with doubt and certainty or uncertainty thus, justifies the asking. Apparently, the switching allows the students to investigate further, to clarify, to verify, or to confirm an earlier knowledge. Through this, they are given the opportunity to explore thus, avail the full utilization of their vernacular in processing a new knowledge from their teacher. Relative to this, one of the respondents simply stated:

“I am an inquisitive student; I ask a lot to clarify because I don’t understand sometimes the language of my teacher. So that I am sure that my question is correct, I am forced to use Ilocano or Filipino ab depende nu anat malagip ko” - HEI3SR2

These findings suggest that code switching can be beneficial to both the students and teachers. From the extracts taken, consequences to teaching and learning can be deduced: clearer view on the part of the students on the concepts being introduced/discussed, higher comprehension among students of the overall instruction, directed decision-making when given choices or alternatives, correct interpretation of the instructions to follow during examinations or activities, the chance to use Filipino and the vernacular in explaining and asking questions, confidence in participating in the class activities and a revitalized joy and pride in using one's vernacular. All of these are directed towards achieving a better performance of the teachers and students.

These findings validate with the conclusions of Olugbara (2008) that students using IsiZulu English code switching interact freely and speak among themselves and they become active and participative in classroom discussions. The teachers, on the other hand, are more flexible, accommodative of students' understanding of their own language and the use of code switching by the teachers and the students play a role in promoting more positive attitudes to the students.

Similarly, Probyn (2001) pointed out that teachers' code switched because the focus is on communicating the concepts in the most comfortable language. As such, the teachers contended that code switching helps students understand everything because it is not a language lesson. Furthermore, they also feel that code switching helps clear some misunderstandings. Furthermore, using a mother tongue inside the classroom when pointing out an idea according to Macaro (2001) and Tang (2002) as cited by Zainil and Arsyad (2021) is less pressuring and time-consuming which will likely lead to a more meaningful discussion.

Finally, Cummins in 1981 asserted that children with high levels of proficiency in two languages show 'positive cognitive effects. In effect, children who come to school speaking more than one language, or who learn a second language in school, will benefit academically as long as both languages are nurtured and developed to the fullest extent.

Implications of the effects of code-switching of instructors and students in Philippine college classrooms

Language is an imperative instrument for the promotion of teaching and learning. It is a vehicle of gaining access to important knowledge and skills, therefore it is the key to cognitive development that can promote or impede scholastic success (Lemmer and Squelech, 1993). Any language can be effectively used to teach provided a methodological approach is followed. If one wants to ensure effective teaching and learning, it must be done in a language that people understand.

Based on the analysis of the extracts in this study, code switching is a big help to facilitate better teaching and learning in Philippine college classrooms. This is substantiated by Tukinoff in 1985 as he claimed that

two languages can be a factor in effective instruction. Furthermore, he asserted that effective teachers make use of every available resource to ensure that students learn. The purpose for language alternation should be tied to achieving effective instruction.

This study however, is only limited to the use of code switching in a Philippine classroom setting. Teachers and students alike also communicate in different contexts and there is no excuse for them to use mixed languages. Hence, the classroom is not only the place to develop the language especially today that the influence of the media is very strong. Simply put, code switching has been developed by both the teachers and students as a means of instruction in the classroom as proven in this study, and as a means of communication outside the school and even in the virtual world. This implies that code switching has become a linguistic trend among Filipinos in different contexts and its continuous prevalence can foster opportunities for people to maximize the use of these languages.

This is substantiated by Tukinoff (1985) as he claimed that two languages can be a factor in effective instruction. Furthermore, he asserted that effective teachers make use of every available resource to ensure that students learn. Further, Bensen and Çavuşoğlu (2013, p. 72) identified code-switching as a means of serving expressions of emotions to build solidarity and good rapport with the students. Thus, the purpose for language alternation should be tied to achieving effective instruction.

In using two or more languages in communication, many claim that mastery and proficiency of such can be affected such that of the occurrences of code switching in this study.

On the contrary, research has shown that a child acquiring two languages simultaneously will make an effort to separate them (to the extent that his proficiencies allow at that particular point in development) when he/she perceives that is what the context requires (Fantini, 1985; Huerta-Macías, 1992; Vihman, 1985).

Hence, an increase in overall use of code switching would encourage students to use it more, simply as a response to the social context. Most importantly, extended use of the students' native language would positively affect their self-esteem.

CONCLUSIONS

This study was limited to the analysis of tertiary classroom oral discourses paying particular attention on the concept and effects of code switching in college classes to identify its implications on language policy formulation and pedagogy. Recordings from classes where English is the medium of instruction like English, Science and Math classes were transcribed and analyzed by the researchers and a Focused Group Discussion (FGD) and an in-depth interview (IDI) with the respondents were also done.

Of the many subjects in college, English, Math and Science were chosen because these subjects are mandated by the Philippine Commission on Higher Education to

use English as the medium of instruction. Based from the results and findings, it can be inferred that code switching can be beneficial to both the students and teachers specifically in Mariano Marcos State University, Laoag City, Ilocos Norte, Philippines. From the extracts taken, effects or consequences to teaching and learning can be deduced: code switching helps students to better understand directions, eradicates language barrier for a clearer instruction, promotes better understanding by students, helps them in generating a better choice, ensures semantic understanding among students, and aids the students to investigate further, to clarify, to verify, or to confirm an earlier knowledge. All of these are directed towards achieving a better performance of the teachers and students.

The number of instances of code switching revealed by this study asserts that it is a natural phenomenon which occurs in any scheme of bilingualism. It is a normal communicative behavior in a bilingual classroom that it can be a useful tool in teaching and learning especially in Philippine college classes.

Thus, it is concluded that code switching exists even in collegiate classes and its prevalence is not only restricted to the basic education sectors. In addition, using code switching in college classes is found to be valuable hence, it is a potent instrument for a better situation of teaching and learning in the Philippine context. Lastly, it is recommended that both teachers and students should continue establishing classroom discourse in accordance with the requirement of the target language learning demands. There is no Declaration of Competing Interest

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